

Google Pixel 3 Setup documentation

Date of Setup: 24th January 2024

Setup by: Daniel Knott

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Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf

First: Basic Settings

- Language Settings (English standard, no change)
- Vision settings (no changes made to standard)
- Emergency call option

Continuing with „Start“

← Vision Settings

You can customize this device to fit your needs. These accessibility features can be changed later in Settings.

Magnification

Zoom in on screen

Font size

Make text larger or smaller

Display size

Make items on screen larger or smaller

Select to Speak

Tap items on your screen to hear them read aloud

TalkBack

Screen reader primarily for people with blindness and low vision

Asked for Sim-Card and Mobile Network

- Pressing „Skip“

Connect to WiFi

- Login to student WiFi with Student ID
- Login successful → checking for updates

Option to copy apps and data from an old phone

- Option to not transfer anything chosen

Copy apps & data

You can choose to transfer your apps, photos, contacts, Google Account, and more.

Don't copy

Next

Setting up new Google Account

- Setting up a new Google account – „create account“ (for personal use)
- Name: Dice
- Gender: Rather not say
- Birthday: 25th April 2000

Screenshots on
following slides

E-Mail: dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

Password: Dice24.01

Asked to add phone number: Decline

Sign in

with your Google Account.

[Learn more about using your account](#)

[Forgot email?](#)

Create account

For my personal use

For my child

For work or my business

[Skip](#)

[Next](#)

Create a Google Account

Enter your name

[Next](#)

Dice | Since | Side

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

q w e r t y u i o p

a s d f g h j k l

↑ z x c v b n m ↵

?123 , 😊 . →

Add phone number?

If you like, you can add this phone's number to your account for use across Google services. [Learn more](#)

For example, your number will be used to

🔑 Reset your password if you forget it

📺 Receive video calls & messages

G Make Google services, including ads, more relevant to you

How it works

📱 To check that your number is current, Google and your carrier may exchange device info, or use background calls or SMS. Standard rates may apply.

🔄 Any number verified on this device will be added to your Google Account

Make Google services, including ads, more relevant to you

How it works

To check that your number is current, Google and your carrier may exchange device info, or use background calls or SMS. Standard rates may apply.

Any number verified on this device will be added to your Google Account

You're in control

This won't make your number public

You can always change your number, control how it's used, or remove it in your Google Account (account.google.com/phone)

[More options](#)

[Skip](#)

[Yes, I'm in](#)

Asked to review account infos

- Next

Review your account info

You can use this email address to sign in later

 Dice
dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

Next

Additional settings: Manual

- Web activity: Keep
- YouTube History: Keep
- Ad personalisation: Show personalised ads
- Get occasional privacy reminders: No

Screenshots on
following slides

Confirm

Choose your settings

- Express (1 step)
Choose your settings in one step. Your choices to turn settings on or off help tailor the content and ad experiences you see.
- Manual (4 steps)
Choose your settings step by step. Your choices to turn settings on or off help tailor the content and ad experiences you see.

You can change your settings anytime at account.google.com

Next

For faster searching, save your Web & App Activity

Step 1 of 4

Choose whether to save Web & App Activity

- Keep until I delete manually
- Keep activity for 18 months and manually delete any time
- Don't save Web & App Activity in my account

What data is used

Web & App Activity saves your activity on Google sites and apps, including searches and associated info like location. It also saves synced Chrome history and activity from sites, apps, and devices that use Google services.

How we use this data

When this setting is on, Web & App Activity saved in your account may be used in any Google service where you're signed in to give you more personalized experiences when using Google products, like faster searching, more relevant results, and app and content

For YouTube homepage recommendations, save your YouTube History

Step 2 of 4

Choose whether to save YouTube History

- Keep until I delete manually
- Keep activity for 36 months and manually delete any time
- Don't save YouTube History in my account

What data is used

YouTube History saves the videos you watch and the things you search for when you use YouTube.

How we use this data

When this setting is on, YouTube History saved in your account may be used in any Google service where you're signed in to personalize your experience, like giving you better recommendations when using YouTube and other Google products, for example articles, apps, YouTube homepage recommendations,

For more tailored ads, turn on personalized ads

Step 3 of 4

Choose whether to turn on personalized ads

- Show me personalized ads**
Tailors the ads you see based on your activity and other data, and lets you block advertisers or ad topics you're not interested in

- Show me generic ads**
You'll still see ads, but they may be less useful, because they'll be based on general factors like the time of day, general location, and content of the page you're looking at

What data is used

We'll tailor ads based on your activity on Google services, such as your queries on Google Search, videos you watch on YouTube, apps you install on your Android device, ads or content you interact with, and associated information like your location. We use information you have provided in your Google Account, such as your age and gender. We'll also use your activity on other sites and apps that use our advertising service.

Calls and notifications will vibrate

How we use this data

Get occasional privacy reminders

Step 4 of 4

Choose whether you want occasional reminders to take a Privacy Checkup and review key privacy settings

- Choose the types of data we save
 - Update what you share with friends or make public
 - Adjust the types of ads you'd like to see
- Privacy reminders**
Get occasional email reminders about these settings

You can change your settings anytime at account.google.com

Back

Next

Confirm your settings

You can change your settings anytime in your Google Account

- Web & App Activity**
This setting will be on
- YouTube History**
This setting will be on
- Personalized ads**
This setting will be on
- Privacy reminders**
Occasional email reminders aren't set

About cookies and similar technologies

We rely on [cookies](#) and similar technologies ("cookies") to remember your settings and other preferences across your signed-in devices. We also use cookies to collect data so we can

- deliver and maintain services, like tracking outages and protecting against spam, fraud, and abuse

Privacy and Terms

- I agree
- Find pdf of privacy policy (download not immediately possible) and terms & conditions attached with presentation

Privacy and Terms

We publish the [Google Terms of Service](#) and the [YouTube Terms of Service](#) (both of which include information about your 14-day withdrawal right) so that you know what to expect as you use Google services, including YouTube. The [Google Play Terms of Service](#) also applies because Google Play helps manage apps on your device. By choosing "I agree" you agree to these terms.

A Google Account allows you to access a range of Google services, such as Gmail and Google Drive. An account also offers access to some additional features that require signing in. For example, when you sign in to Google Maps, you can save your "Home" and "Work" addresses. And when you sign in to YouTube, you can like videos, subscribe to channels, and create your own YouTube channel. Google's Terms of Service apply to [this list of services](#), a list that also provides links to service-specific additional terms and policies that explain what you can expect from using Google services, and what we expect from you.

And remember, [Google's Privacy Policy](#) describes how Google handles information generated as you use Google services.

It also includes information about why we process data, such as when we are pursuing legitimate interests while applying appropriate safeguards that protect your

Privacy and Terms

We publish the [Google Terms of Service](#) and the [YouTube Terms of Service](#) (both of which include information about your 14-day withdrawal right) so that you know what to expect as you use Google services, including YouTube. The [Google Play Terms of Service](#) also applies because Google Play helps manage apps on your device. By choosing "I agree" you agree to these terms.

A Google Account allows you to access a range of Google services, such as Gmail and Google Drive. An account also offers access to some additional features that require signing in. For example, when you sign in to Google Maps, you can save your "Home" and "Work" addresses. And when you sign in to YouTube, you can like videos, subscribe to channels, and create your own YouTube channel. Google's Terms of Service apply to [this list of services](#), a list that also provides links to service-specific additional terms and policies that explain what you can expect from using Google services, and what we expect from you.

And remember, [Google's Privacy Policy](#) describes how Google handles information generated as you use Google services.

It also includes information about why we process data, such as when we are pursuing legitimate interests while applying appropriate safeguards that protect your privacy. This means that we process your information for things like:

- Providing, maintaining, and improving our services to meet the needs of our users
- Developing new products and features that are useful for our users
- Understanding how people use our services to ensure and improve the performance of our services

Privacy and Terms

We publish the [Google Terms of Service](#) and the [YouTube Terms of Service](#) (both of which include information about your 14-day withdrawal right) so that you know what to expect as you use Google services, including YouTube. The [Google Play Terms of Service](#) also applies because Google Play helps manage apps on your device. By choosing "I agree" you agree to these terms.

A Google Account allows you to access a range of Google services, such as Gmail and Google Drive. An account also offers access to some additional features that require signing in. For example, when you sign in to Google Maps, you can save your "Home" and "Work" addresses. And when you sign in to YouTube, you can like videos, subscribe to channels, and create your own YouTube channel. Google's Terms of Service apply to [this list of services](#), a list that also provides links to service-specific additional terms and policies that explain what you can expect from using Google services, and what we expect from you.

And remember, [Google's Privacy Policy](#) describes how Google handles information generated as you use Google services.

It also includes information about why we process data, such as when we are pursuing legitimate interests while applying appropriate safeguards that protect your privacy. This means that we process your information for things like:

- Customizing our services to provide you with a better user experience (and, if relevant, adapting the experience to be age-appropriate)
- Marketing to inform users about our services
- Providing advertising, which allows us to offer many of our services at no cost (and when ads are personalized, we ask for your consent)
- Detecting, preventing, or otherwise addressing fraud, abuse, security, or technical issues with our services
- Protecting against harm to the rights, property or safety of Google, our users, or the public as required or permitted by law, including disclosing information to government authorities
- Performing research that improves our services for our users and benefits the public
- Fulfilling obligations to our partners like developers and rights holders
- Enforcing legal claims, including investigation of potential violations of applicable Terms of Service

You can visit your Google Account ([account.google.com](#)) to take a Privacy Checkup or to adjust your privacy controls.

Have questions? [Contact us](#)

[Don't create the account](#) [I agree](#)

Date & Time

- Entering correct data
- continue

Date & time

Adjust if needed.

Berlin
GMT+01:00

Date
Wed, Jan 24, 2024

Time
4:38 PM

Next

Google Services

- Backup to Google Drive
- Use location
- Allow scanning
- Diagnostic Data

All agreed to

The image displays three sequential screenshots of the Google Services settings interface on an Android device. The top status bar shows signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery icons. The main content area features the Google logo and the text "Google Services" with the email address "dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com". Below this, there are three sections: "Backup & storage", "Location", and "Device maintenance". Each section contains a list of services with their respective settings (checked/unchecked) and a toggle switch. The "More" button is visible at the bottom of the first two screenshots, and the "Accept" button is visible at the bottom of the third screenshot. The text "All agreed to" is overlaid on the left side of the image.

Google Services
dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com
Tap to learn more about each service, such as how to turn it on or off later. Data will be used according to Google's [Privacy Policy](#).

Backup & storage

- Back up to Google Drive Easily restore your data or switch devices at any time. Your backup includes apps, app data, call history, contacts, device settings (including Wi-Fi passwords and permissions), and SMS & MMS messages.

Your backups are securely encrypted and uploaded to Google. For some data, your device's screen lock PIN, pattern or password is used for enhanced protection.

Location

- Use location Allow apps and services with location permission to use your device's location. Google may collect location data periodically and use this data in an anonymous way to improve location accuracy and location-based services.
- Allow scanning Allow apps and services to scan for Wi-Fi networks and nearby devices at any time, even when Wi-Fi or Bluetooth is off.

Device maintenance

- Send usage and diagnostic data Help improve your Android device experience by automatically sending diagnostic, device, and app usage data to Google. This will help battery life, system and app stability, and other improvements. Some aggregate data will also help Google apps and partners, such as Android Web & App Activity setting is turned on, this data may be saved to your Google Account.
- Install updates & apps By continuing, you agree that this device may also automatically download and install updates and apps from Google, your carrier, and your device's manufacturer, possibly using cellular data. Data rates may apply. Some of these apps may offer in-app purchases.

Tap "Accept" to confirm your selection of these Google services settings.

More **Accept** **Accept**

Screenlock

- Fingerprint: Skip
- Code set to 1234
(no Screenshot taken)

Unlock with Pixel Imprint

Use your fingerprint to unlock your phone or approve purchases.

Note: Your fingerprint may be less secure than a strong pattern or PIN.

Skip

Next

Continue Setup?

- Continue

Continued Setup

Screenshots on
following slides

- Google Assistant: Turn on
- Voice Match: No thanks (Screenshot missing)
- Squeeze: Do it later
- Google Pay: Skip
- Always on display: Notifications added to lockscreen (Screenshot missing)
- Anything else: No thanks
- Last tips: All set

Google Assistant

The new way to talk to Google

Check traffic to work

Help your Assistant customize your experience by turning on these settings.

dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

App info from your devices ▼

Saves information about the apps installed on your signed-in devices to make them easier to interact with when

No thanks

Turn on

Do it later

Next

No thanks

Squeeze for your Assistant

To talk to your Assistant at any time, quickly squeeze the bottom half of your phone, then release

Anything else?

Set up a few more things now, or find them later in Settings

Add another email account

Change font size

Change wallpaper

Control info on lock screen

Discover songs with Now Playing

Review additional apps

One last tip

For support, tips and tricks, and more, go to Settings > Tips & support

Get Pixel tips, updates on Google products, and share feedback. Unsubscribe any time.

All set

Home Screen

- Visible apps on home screen
 - Phone calls
 - Messages
 - Google Play
 - Google Chrome
 - There was no option to pick a (different) browser
 - Camera
 - Google search bar
 - There was no option to pick a (different) search engine

Initial Layout

- Very few preinstalled apps

First Google Search

- Search for „dice hhu“

First use of browser (google chrome)

- Agree to terms and conditions – accept all
- Signing in with google account

Hi, Dice

dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

Sign in to Chrome

Sign in with your Google Account to get your bookmarks, history, passwords, and other settings on all your devices.

dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com ✓

Add account

Chrome Sync
Your bookmarks, history, passwords, and other settings will be synced to your Google Account so you can use them on all your devices

Personalize Google services
Google may use your browsing history to personalize Search, ads, and other Google services

Manage Chrome Sync and personalization in [Settings](#)

NO THANKS

CONTINUE

UNDO

OK, GOT IT

Options in Google Chrome

- Google as standard search engine
- Recommendations for: Facebook, YouTube, Amazon, Wikipedia, ESPN, Yahoo, Ebay and Instagram
 - No other browsers but products from other companies
- No news articles appear

Google play store

- Get started: Linking Google services
 - New EU laws require consent to link Google services starting March 6th
 - Choices will take effect on March 6th
- No, don't keep linked
- Several apps recommended through different options
- No new app installed

4:58

D dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

Keep your Google services, like Google Play, linked?

Google Play Search

YouTube Ad services

Chrome Google Shopping

Google Maps

New laws in the EU mean that, starting on March 6, 2024, Google needs your consent if you want to keep these services linked. When linked, they can share data with each other and with all other Google services to:

- Combine data to help personalize content and ads
- Develop and improve our services
- Measure and improve the delivery of ads
- Perform other purposes described in Google's Privacy Policy at g.co/privacypolicy

Things to know

Other settings let you control whether you see personalized content or ads. Linking Google services is not about sharing your data with third-party services

4:59

Things to know

Other settings let you control whether you see personalized content or ads. Linking Google services is not about sharing your data with third-party services

If services aren't linked, some features that involve sharing data across Google services will be limited

For example, if you have personalization on for a service in your privacy settings but don't link that service, you won't get personalization based on data from other services, but can still get personalization based on data from that service

Aspects of a service that don't involve sharing data won't be affected

You won't be signed out of any Google services if you choose not to link services

What data is used

All types of personal data described in Google's Privacy Policy can be shared across linked Google services

What's not changing

Even if they're not linked, Google services can always share data with each other to prevent fraud and abuse, effectively help you complete tasks, and for certain other purposes

You're in control. You can change your choices anytime in your Google Account. Choices will take effect on March 6, 2024. [Learn more about linked services](#)

4:59

What data is used

All types of personal data described in Google's Privacy Policy can be shared across linked Google services

For example, searches, videos you watch on YouTube, apps you install from Google Play, and associated info, like your device info, can be shared across linked services

This consent applies to your data and services when you are signed in

What's not changing

Even if they're not linked, Google services can always share data with each other to prevent fraud and abuse, effectively help you complete tasks, and for certain other purposes

Other purposes for which shared data may always be used include protecting against spam and complying with the law

You're in control. You can change your choices anytime in your Google Account. Choices will take effect on March 6, 2024. [Learn more about linked services](#)

Yes, keep linked

No, don't keep linked

For you Your apps, games, payment methods, notifications and offers are now here

Update available

Explore the path to your wellness
New year, new you

 Headspace: Sleep & M...
Headspace for Meditation...
4.3 ★ USK: All ages **Install**
In-app purchases

Sponsored · Suggested for you

- TikTok: Videos, Lives & Musik
Social · Networking
4.0 ★
- MISTPLAY: Play to Earn Rewards
Entertainment
4.2 ★

Your choice will take effect on March 6, 2024. You can change your choices anytime in your Google Account.

For you Top charts Kids Categories

Update available

Jump into self-focus and learning
New year, new you

 Babbel - Learn Langu...
Babbel
4.6 ★ USK: All ages **Install**
In-app purchases

Sponsored · Suggested for you

- TikTok: Videos, Lives & Musik
Social · Networking
4.0 ★
- MISTPLAY: Play to Earn Rewards
Entertainment
4.2 ★

- imo-International Calls & Chat
4.3 ★
- WhatsApp Messenger
4.0 ★
- Spotify: Music and Podcasts
4.3 ★
- waipu.tv - Live TV-Streaming
4.4 ★
- Instagram
4.0 ★
- TikTok: Videos, Lives & Musik
4.0 ★
- Snapchat
3.8 ★
- Facebook
3.2 ★
- Netflix
3.5 ★
-
-
-

- WhatsApp Messenger
4.0 ★
- Instagram
4.0 ★
- Telegram
4.4 ★
- Snapchat
3.8 ★
- Spotify: Music and Podcasts
4.3 ★
- TikTok: Videos, Lives & Musik
4.0 ★
- Facebook
3.2 ★
- Netflix
3.5 ★
- Messenger
3.9 ★
-
-
-

List of default apps

- Google Chrome, Google Pay, Google assistant → preinstalled
 - No alternatives offered

Setting up Gmail

- Dice E-Mail already installed
- Option: Add new E-Mails from different providers

Dice
dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

+ Add another email address

TAKE ME TO GMAIL

5:05

← Help

Add another email account to the Gmail app

Read and send mail from Yahoo, Hotmail, and other email addresses using the Gmail app, instead of forwarding your mail.

Want to get more out of Google apps at work or school? [Sign up for a Google Workspace trial at no charge](#).

With your non-Google address, you can use many of the same Gmail features as Google Accounts:

- Search for an email by sender, subject, or other criteria.
- Move an email to a folder.
- [Change how you see reply emails.](#)

Android iPhone & iPad

Add or remove your account

You can add both Gmail and non-Gmail accounts

5:05

← Help

- Search for an email by sender, subject, or other criteria.
- Move an email to a folder.
- [Change how you see reply emails.](#)

Android iPhone & iPad

Add or remove your account

You can add both Gmail and non-Gmail accounts to the Gmail app for Android.

[Add an account](#)

[Remove an account](#)

See messages from all accounts in Gmail app

1. On your Android phone or tablet, open the Gmail app.
2. In the top left, tap Menu.
3. Tap **All inboxes**.

5:05

← Help

See messages from all accounts in Gmail app

1. On your Android phone or tablet, open the Gmail app.
2. In the top left, tap Menu.
3. Tap **All inboxes**.

I'm getting an error

- "Username and password not accepted"
- "Email security not guaranteed"
- Certificate error
- "Something went wrong" or "Couldn't open connection to server"

Related resources

- [Create a Gmail account](#)
- [Change or reset your password](#)
- [Sign in to Gmail](#)

✓ Tap a sender image to select that conversation. ✕

T **The Google Account team** 4:38 PM
Information about your new Google Acco...
Access your account features and services. ... ☆

New in Gmail

All the features you love with a fresh new look

GOT IT

Trying to download an app outside the play store

Screenshots on following slides

- Download through chip.de
- Allowing Chrome to access files
- Downloading Fortnite Installer
 - This can harm your device, download anyway? → Continue

Avast Secure Browser
Leistungsstarke Werbeblocker
Surfen sie bis zu 4x schneller mit dem von Chip empfohlenen Browser. [KOSTENLOS DOWNLOADEN](#)

HOME > ... > ANDROID APPS > SPIELE

Fortnite - Battle Royale APK - Android App

DOWNLOAD
FORTNITE - BATTLE ROYALE APK - ANDROID APP

Falls der Download nicht beginnt, **klicken Sie**

GERMAN ENGLISH

Avast Secure Browser
Leistungsstarke Werbeblocker
Surfen sie bis zu 4x schneller mit dem von Chip empfohlenen Browser. [KOSTENLOS DOWNLOADEN](#)

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Fortnite - Battle Royale APK - Android App

DOWNLOAD
FORTNITE - BATTLE ROYALE APK - ANDROID APP

Falls der Download nicht beginnt, **klicken Sie**

GERMAN ENGLISH

Downloads

Today - Jan 24, 2024

FortniteInstaller-5.3.0.apk
Downloading... 100%

Warning

- Allow Chrome to install unknown apps
- Installation successful after granting permission

Screenshots on
following slides

Comparison with prior setup in october

- Connection to Student WiFi was possible (slide 4)
- Option to adjust date and time (slide 13)
- No news articles appear when starting browser (slide 24)
- Choice whether to interlink google services according to EU legislation (slides 25, 26)
- Option to add E-Mail addresses from different providers (slide 29)